

Global Quantification of the Dispersion Effect with POLDER Satellite Data

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Abstract

Increased aerosols can modify the shape of the cloud Particle Size Distribution (PSD), thereby influencing the radiative properties of clouds, known as the Dispersion Effect (DE). However, a global, observation-based quantification of its impact on Aerosol-Cloud Interactions (ACI) is lacking, leading to DE being typically ignored in satellite-based estimates of ACI forcing. Here we propose a physics-based method that combines polarimetric satellite data on cloud PSD to achieve global observational quantification of DE's impact on ACI in liquid-phase stratiform clouds. Globally, DE offsets ACI changes induced by droplet number concentration variation and liquid water path adjustment by 7% and -1.4% , respectively. Furthermore, a parameterization based on the global dataset of PSD shape parameters is developed to improve DE estimation in large-scale models. Both the quantification and parameterization enhance our understanding of DE and facilitate the inclusion of this non-negligible impact of DE on ACI in estimating aerosol climate forcing.

Introduction

The increase in anthropogenic aerosols affects the radiative properties of liquid clouds by altering their microphysical (cloud droplet concentration, N_d , and effective radius, R_e) and macrophysical (liquid water path, LWP , and liquid cloud fraction, f) properties, phenomena generically known as Aerosol-Cloud Interactions (ACI). Additional aerosols cause a monotonic increase in N_d and, given a constant LWP , a decrease in R_e , leading to a net cooling effect on the earth-atmosphere system, referred to as the Twomey effect¹. Subsequently, LWP and f respond to changes in N_d , and R_e , known as rapid adjustments of ACI^{2,3}, which, together with the Twomey effect, contribute to estimating the effective radiative forcing due to ACI (ERF_{aci}). An example of such an adjustment is the cloud lifetime effect^{4,5}. The latest report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change pointed out that ACI is one of the largest sources of uncertainty in current climate assessments⁶.

In fact, besides N_d , the shape of cloud Particle Size Distribution (PSD) is also a key factor influencing the Twomey effect. Increased aerosols change the cloud PSD shape, impacting cloud albedo and thus contributing to ERF_{aci} , referred to as the Dispersion Effect (DE). Liu and Daum⁷

41 analyzed marine clouds sampled by aircraft and pointed out that the DE can offset the number
 42 effect (i.e., considering only the impact of N_d changes on R_e in the Twomey effect) by 10 ~ 80%.
 43 As research progressed, aircraft-based studies found such discrepant results that DE not only
 44 offsets ACI^{8,9} but may also enhance it¹⁰⁻¹³ or have no significant impact^{14,15}. Considering the
 45 regional nature and significant uncertainty of the DE, this effect is typically ignored when
 46 estimating ERF_{aci} based on satellite observations^{3,16}.

47 By using parameterizations derived from the regional aircraft data in General Circulation Models
 48 (GCMs), the global impact of DE on ACI can be estimated. For instance, modelers applied
 49 different parameterizations¹⁷⁻²¹ in GCMs and found DE can offset the number effect by -13 ~
 50 35%^{9,17,22}; Xie et al.²³ incorporated three parameterizations^{17,19,20} into a GCM and demonstrated
 51 that DE could offset approximately 7 ~ 14% of ACI globally. The high uncertainty in model
 52 evaluations may be related to the use of regionally dependent cloud PSD parameterizations.
 53 Additionally, GCM results can only provide the range of DE variations and generally lack
 54 observational validation on a global scale.

55 DE can be characterized as the sensitivity of the cloud PSD parameter (commonly represented by
 56 the ratio of effective radius to volume-mean radius, β) to the increasing aerosol number
 57 concentration (N_a)^{24,25}. However, it is challenging to simultaneously obtain both β and N_a in
 58 clouds, so some cloud variables are commonly used as proxies for N_a . In the early stages, N_d was
 59 widely used^{9,17,20}. As research progressed, it was found that changes in the liquid water content per
 60 cloud droplet (i.e., LWC/N_d , hereafter LN) could better reflect DE, with a power-law
 61 relationship^{19,26}:

$$62 \quad \beta = a(LN)^b, \quad (1)$$

63 where a and b are fitting parameters and DE is closely related to the parameter b ¹⁹. Therefore, the
 64 key to quantifying DE is obtaining β and LN , thereby determining parameter b .

65 The data of β and LN used in previous studies were mainly obtained through regional aircraft
 66 observations^{9,17,19,20,27}, which makes DE quantification lack global representativeness. In satellite
 67 observations, the cloud PSD is typically described by R_e and the effective variance (V_e), with V_e
 68 being often fixed or discrete^{28,29}, which hinders the global analysis of DE. Recently, a global
 69 dataset with both R_e and continuous V_e available from the POLarization and Directionality of
 70 Earth's Reflectances (POLDER) instrument was established using artificial neural networks
 71 (NNs)³⁰ (hereafter, POLDER-NNs, see Methods), allowing us to provide a global estimate of the
 72 impact of DE on ACI.

73 Two steps are proposed for the global quantification (see Methods for more details):

74 Step 1: Using R_e and V_e retrieved by POLDER-NNs over global regions dominated by liquid-
 75 phase stratiform clouds, the cloud-top β and LN can be determined as

$$76 \quad \beta_P = [(1 - V_e)(1 - 2V_e)]^{-1/3}, \quad LN_P = A(1 - V_e)(1 - 2V_e)R_e^3. \quad (2)$$

77 Here, the subscript P indicates calculations based on the POLDER-NNs dataset, $A = 4\pi\rho_w/3$,
 78 where ρ_w is the water density. By using β_P and LN_P for parameter fitting in equation (1), a cloud
 79 PSD parameterization based on global observations can be obtained.

80 Step 2: In adiabatic clouds, the cloud optical thickness (τ_c) depends on cloud-top β and N_d , as
 81 well as LWP ($\tau_c \propto \beta^{-1}LWP^{5/6}N_d^{1/3}$)³¹. By using the adiabatic liquid water lapse rate (c_w) to
 82 relate LWP to cloud-top LWC , τ_c can be fully expressed in terms of cloud-top variables, leading

83 to $\tau_c \propto \beta^{-1} LWC^{5/3} N_d^{1/3}$. Given that β follows equation (1), based on the calculation of ERF_{aci}
84 ³, the impacts of DE on the number effect (DO_{Nd} , i.e., the impact of instantaneous DE) and the
85 *LWP* adjustment effect (DO_{LWP} , i.e., the impact of adjusted DE) can be expressed as

$$86 \quad DO_{Nd} = -3b \cdot 100 \%, DO_{LWP} = \frac{3}{5}b \cdot 100 \%, \quad (3)$$

87 where *DO* stands for the Dispersion Offset (in %), and *b* can be derived from step 1.

88 **Results and Discussion**

89 **Global distribution of DE's impact on ACI**

90 First, we use POLDER-NNs data over global regions dominated by liquid-phase stratiform clouds
91 to calculate the spatial distribution of the parameter *b*, and based on this, derive the global
92 distributions of DO_{Nd} and DO_{LWP} , as shown in Fig. 1.

93 The variables directly provided by the POLDER-NNs dataset are presented in Fig. 1a, b, including
94 R_e and V_e . The β_p and LN_p calculated from R_e and V_e are shown in Fig. 1c, d. Overall, the spatial
95 distribution of β_p is similar to that of V_e , while LN_p is similar to R_e . Specifically, both β_p and LN_p
96 exhibit distinct land-ocean distribution characteristics, which align with our general understanding
97 of these variables (see Methods). By fitting a power-law relationship between β_p and LN_p within
98 each grid point, the parameter *b* can be determined (Fig. 1e). The dotted areas indicate that the
99 fitting relationships are statistically significant with a 95% confidence level. Overall, the spatial
100 distribution of parameter *b* exhibits two characteristics: 1) *b* values across different grid points are
101 predominantly negative; 2) there is significant spatial variability for parameter *b*. Next, we conduct
102 further analysis focusing on the two characteristics.

103 In detail, the proportion of negative *b* values fitted using POLDER data exceeds 97% (with the
104 dotted areas being 100%) (Supplementary Fig. 1). However, the parameter *b* calculated through
105 aircraft observations could be negative¹⁹ or positive²⁶. We think the discrepancy is likely due to
106 the fact that the previous in-situ measurements were primarily of local/regional scale with higher
107 spatial resolution compared to the POLDER-NNs³⁰. Aircraft in-situ observations typically cover a
108 range of kilometers, capturing fine-scale variations of β to LN within clouds. Lu et al.³² and Zhang
109 et al.³³ demonstrated, through in-situ observations and numerical simulations, that the cloud PSD
110 parameter shows a positive correlation with LN for small cloud droplets. The relatively coarse
111 spatial grid of the POLDER-NNs can only capture the dominant large-scale relationship,
112 overshadowing the less frequent positive correlations and leading to our generally negative
113 calculated *b* values (Fig. 1e). However, since the grid scale used in GCMs is also relatively coarse
114 and reflects the overall conditions within large-scale grids of hundreds of kilometers, these results
115 are appropriately matched for model evaluations.

116 Additionally, there is significant spatial dependency in the distribution of *b* values across different
117 grid points (with a standard deviation of 0.015, and 0.013 within the dotted areas). Overall, more
118 negative *b* values are predominantly concentrated in regions heavily influenced by anthropogenic
119 aerosols, indicating that the PSD shape response to aerosol changes is more sensitive in these
120 regions. To explain the spatial distribution of *b*, we plotted the relative changes of β_p and LN_p
121 (Supplementary Fig. 2). Analysis revealed that the parameter *b* over land is determined by the
122 combined variations of β_p and LN_p , while over ocean, it is primarily determined by the variations

123 in β_p (see Methods). However, current GCMs do not consider spatial variations in the parameter
124 b , which could introduce biases in simulating the cloud PSD and DE.

125 The spatial distribution of b can be used to estimate the spatial distribution of DO_{Nd} and DO_{LWP}
126 (Fig. 1f, g), indicating that the impacts of instantaneous and adjusted DE also exhibit spatial
127 variability. Considering only regions with high-reliability b values (dotted areas), DE globally
128 exhibits a 9.3% offset on the number effect and a 1.86% enhancement on LWP adjustment effect.

129 Overall assessment of DE's impact on ACI

130 Next, we examine all POLDER-NNs data collected throughout the year over global regions
131 dominated by liquid-phase stratiform clouds. By fitting β_p and LN_p calculated from all the data,
132 we find that they exhibit a clear power-law relationship (Pearson correlation coefficient $r = -0.53$,
133 $p < 0.01$), with the fitting equation being $\beta_p = 0.68LN_p^{-0.024}$ (Fig. 2a). According to equation (3)
134 and $b = -0.024$, DE can offset 7.2% of the number effect but enhance the LWP adjustment effect
135 by 1.44%.

136 Considering the impact of underlying surfaces on the cloud PSD, we further conduct regressions
137 for land and ocean separately (Fig. 2b, c). The b values are -0.026 for land and -0.028 for ocean.
138 Correspondingly, the values of DO_{Nd} and DO_{LWP} are 7.8%, -1.56% for land and 8.4%, -1.68% for
139 ocean. Specifically, the mean LN_p for the land (5.2 ng) is lower than that for ocean (7.3 ng), but
140 the mean β_p for the land is slightly higher (1.098 vs. 1.095). Overall, the impact of underlying
141 surfaces on the parameter b is insignificant, changing the b value by only about 0.002.

142 A linear regression in log-to-log space is applied to all the satellite data directly in the above
143 analyses. However, a more widely used approach for calculating the sensitivity between two
144 variables with huge amounts of satellite data is the pre-binned method^{16,34-36}. Here, we also use
145 the pre-binned method to fit parameter b , as shown in Fig. 2d-f. The values of parameter b in
146 global, land, and ocean regions are -0.020, -0.024, and -0.023, with $|r|$ not less than 0.87,
147 demonstrating a stronger power-law relationship. Comparing these with Fig. 2a-c, the absolute
148 biases between the two methods for global, land, and ocean regions are 0.004, 0.002, and 0.005,
149 respectively, suggesting that the calculation method of the fitting parameter influences the results,
150 particularly in ocean regions. Additionally, the empirical power-law appears to fit the oceanic data
151 better than the land data in the pre-binned method, which is more susceptible to extreme values.
152 We speculate that this is mainly related to retrieval algorithm challenges in accurately retrieving
153 large cloud droplets. Compared to oceanic regions, retrieval uncertainty for large cloud droplets
154 over land is greater³⁰. This increased uncertainty may cause β_p over land to become less sensitive
155 to LN_p with a value greater than 5 ng (see Methods), thereby weakening the fitted correlation
156 coefficient (Fig. 2e).

157 Quantitative Analysis of Uncertainty

158 Currently, the quantifiable sources of uncertainty include: 1) the inherent limitations of the
159 POLDER-NNs³⁰; 2) cloud heterogeneity³⁷; 3) the retrieval method, wavelength, and grid scale²⁹;
160 and 4) the fitting method for parameter b ³⁴. Based on previous studies, we determined the
161 uncertainty range of b caused by different sources by considering a bias-corrected random
162 Gaussian noise (Fig. 3a). Subsequently, a Monte Carlo method³⁸ was applied to evaluate the
163 overall impact of the four uncertainty sources on the estimation of b . It was assumed that the b
164 values associated with each source follow a normal distribution. A random sampling process was

165 conducted 10 million times, and for each iteration, the mean b value influenced by the different
166 sources was calculated, resulting in a probability density distribution of b (Fig. 3b). The mean of
167 this distribution is taken as the best estimate of b , while the 5 ~ 95% confidence interval is used to
168 represent the uncertainty range. A detailed description of the method is provided in the Methods
169 section.

170 The results show that the best estimate of the b (with 5 ~ 95% uncertainty in parentheses) is -0.024
171 (-0.026 ~ -0.022) globally, -0.025 (-0.028 ~ -0.022) over land, and -0.029 (-0.031 ~ -0.026) over
172 ocean. The corresponding DO_{Nd} values are 7.2% (6.6 ~ 7.8%), 7.5% (6.6 ~ 8.4%), and 8.7% (7.8
173 ~ 9.3%), and the DO_{LWP} values are -1.44% (-1.56 ~ -1.32%), -1.50% (-1.68 ~ -1.32%), and -1.74%
174 (-1.86 ~ -1.56%), respectively, as shown in the Table 1. This indicates that the dispersion effect
175 caused by increased aerosols offsets the number effect by approximately 7% and enhances the
176 LWP adjustment effect by about 1.4% globally, with a stronger impact on clouds over the ocean.

177 **Comparison with previous studies**

178 This section compares b and DO obtained by POLDER-NNs with those by aircraft and GCMs
179 (Table 1). In most studies, the b values were derived from aircraft observations and DO values
180 estimated in GCMs (an exception is the study by Liu and Daum⁷ which derived DO from aircraft
181 data and theoretical estimation).

182 The aircraft data used to fit b in previous studies were conducted in various regions. For instance,
183 Liu et al.¹⁹ obtained a value of -0.14 by analyzing aircraft observations sampled in North America.
184 Martins and Silva Dias²⁶ fitted the relationship between β and LN by studying clouds in Amazon,
185 obtaining a value of 0.072. In this study, whether fitting globally different regions as a whole (-
186 0.026 ~ -0.022) or fitting data separately within each grid and then calculating the global mean (-
187 0.031 ± 0.013), the b values fall within the range of previously fitted b values using aircraft
188 observations (Table 1). Additionally, the b values calculated in this study are predominantly
189 negative across various global regions, and their absolute values are smaller compared to previous
190 results.

191 Previous studies primarily focused on the impact of instantaneous DE (i.e., DO_{Nd}), as shown in
192 Table 1. In the early stages, Liu and Daum⁷ suggested that DO_{Nd} could even reach 80%. However,
193 as research progressed, the values for DO_{Nd} consistently decreased. Recent research based on
194 GCMs shows that the impact of instantaneous DE ranges from -13% (enhancement) to 35%
195 (offset)^{9,17,22}. Our results (6.6 ~ 7.8%) fall within the range of DO_{Nd} calculated by previous
196 studies. However, previous estimations could only provide a range of DO_{Nd} calculated from
197 different parameterizations, without validation with global observations. The DO_{Nd} obtained in
198 this study could be a validation reference for the assessment of parameterizations, contributing to
199 further improvements and developments in GCMs.

200 Previous parameterizations derived from aircraft in-situ observations are all at a local/regional
201 scale, which partially meets the requirements for global simulations conducted by GCMs. This
202 study utilizes satellite data to obtain a global-scale fitting parameterization ($\beta = 0.68LN^{-0.024}$ or
203 $\beta = 0.73LN^{-0.020}$, see Fig. 2), which better meets the requirements for GCM applications. In the
204 future, the parameterization is expected to enhance the models' ability to simulate cloud PSD for
205 liquid-phase stratiform clouds, thereby reducing the uncertainty in climate assessments.

206 To ensure the robustness and applicability of the conclusions, the following sections provide a
207 detailed discussion of the assumptions, causal interpretation, limitations, and implications for
208 future ACI studies.

209 **Assumption of adiabaticity of clouds**

210 The derivation of DO is dependent on the assumption that the observed clouds are under moist
211 adiabatic conditions, wherein clouds are not subject to the entrainment-mixing process. According
212 to the dependence of optical depth on the adiabatic liquid water lapse rate (c_w) in equation (15) as
213 $c_w^{-1/6}$, variations in sub-adiabaticity due to entrainment-mixing are unlikely to significantly affect
214 the albedo or the results of this study when modifying the overall c_w in the cloud (equation (16)).

215 **Causal analysis of aerosol effects on LN and β**

216 First, this causal relationship aligns with the physical understanding of cloud microphysical
217 processes. The formation of the cloud PSD is primarily controlled by, until collision-coalescence
218 sets in, the condensation growth process^{19,21}. And the negative relationship basically reflects the
219 fact that condensation leads to a narrow size distribution as droplets grow. The empirical
220 relationship between LN and β was demonstrated by Wood³⁹, which was later supported by the
221 theoretical analysis of Liu et al.⁴⁰ and further validated by aircraft observations from several
222 campaigns by Liu et al.¹⁹. A significant relationship obtained using POLDER-NNs to some extent
223 validates this assumption (Figs. 1 and 2). Therefore, we think the co-varying relationship between
224 β and LN has solid physics behind it, instead of being an observational artifact.

225 In addition, this causal relationship can also be confirmed through statistical analysis. To examine
226 the relationship between aerosols, we employ a POLDER aerosol product⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ to calculate the
227 aerosol index (AI) and plot joint histograms of AI versus LN and β (See Methods). As shown in
228 Fig. 4a, b, AI and LN exhibit a negative power-law relationship, whereas AI and β show an
229 overall positive power-law correlation, which is consistent with theoretical analysis. When aerosol
230 increases and the LWC in the cloud remains relatively stable, the liquid water per cloud droplet
231 (LN) decreases. At the same time, β increases overall with AI , aligning with most previous studies
232 that reported aerosol-induced broadening of the cloud PSD^{7,9,19,20}. Given the negative power-law
233 relationship between LN and β (Fig. 2), it is hypothesized that LN plays a crucial mediating role
234 in the impact of AI on β .

235 To investigate this, we conducted a Causal Mediation Analysis⁴⁵ to examine the role of LN as a
236 mediator in AI 's impact on β , with the results shown in Fig. 4c (see Methods). The average causal
237 mediation impact (0.0037) indicates the influence of AI on β transmitted through the mediator
238 LN , while the average direct impact (0.0041) represents the direct influence of AI on β . The total
239 impact is 0.0078, and all results are statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The results indicate that
240 LN plays a significant mediating role in the impact of AI on β , further supporting the causality of
241 the findings.

242 **Limitations of this study**

243 Some limitations of this study need to be pointed out. First, due to the limited data resolution and
244 the predefined data filtering criteria, this study mainly focuses on liquid-phase stratiform clouds,
245 which account for over 78% of the samples (see Methods and Supplementary Fig. 3). Accordingly,
246 the cloud PSD analysis, quantification of the dispersion effect, and parameterization proposed in

247 this work are primarily applicable to liquid-phase stratiform clouds. While some large-scale
248 cumulus clouds are included, the relevance of our findings to typical cumulus clouds remains
249 uncertain and warrants further investigation using higher-resolution satellite observations⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸
250 (e.g., from the Multi-viewing Multi-channel Multi-polarization Imaging⁴⁹). Given that cumulus
251 clouds generally play a less significant role in ACI⁵⁰, our focus aligns with the core objectives of
252 current ACI research. Second, the analysis in this study is limited to one year of data (2006).
253 Longer-term datasets are needed in the future for further validation and trend analysis. Finally,
254 although the β values calculated based on V_e fall within the uncertainty range of previous studies,
255 the V_e in POLDER-NNs has only been compared with synthetic data and has not yet been validated
256 against observational data. Despite these limitations, the quantitative method and analytical
257 framework proposed in this study can still provide valuable insights for future DE research.

258 **Implications for future ACI estimation**

259 Additional aerosols can modify the shape of cloud PSD, thereby modifying the cloud albedo and
260 forcing, a phenomenon known as the Dispersion Effect (DE). However, this effect is typically
261 ignored when calculating the ERF_{aci} , largely due to a lack of global quantitative estimations of
262 DE's impact on ACI. To address the gap, this study proposed a quantitative method based on
263 physical mechanisms, utilizing physical equations and theoretical derivations. By using POLDER
264 satellite observations, this study quantifies the global impact of DE on ACI over regions dominated
265 by liquid-phase stratiform clouds. Based on a comprehensive analysis from multiple perspectives,
266 it can be concluded that DE offsets the number effect by approximately 7% but enhances the LWP
267 adjustment effect by around 1.4% on a global scale. Hence, the DE has a non-negligible impact on
268 ACI, necessitating its consideration in future ERF_{aci} calculation.

269

270

271 **Methods**

272 **POLDER retrievals**

273 The POLARization and Directionality of Earth's Reflectances (POLDER) instrument, here in its
274 version mounted on the PARASOL (Polarization and Anisotropy of Reflectances for Atmospheric
275 Science coupled with Observations from a Lidar) microsatellite⁵¹, provides global cloud properties
276 by multi-angle polarimetric observations⁵²⁻⁵⁴. Thanks to the polarimetric measurements, POLDER
277 can retrieve two pieces of information on the cloud PSD at the cloud top, namely, besides the cloud
278 effective radius (R_e), also the effective variance (V_e)^{55,56}.

279 Recently, Di Noia et al.³⁰ introduced a neural network algorithm (NNs) to utilize multi-angle and
280 multi-wavelength polarimetric measurements from POLDER Level-1 data (5 km × 6 km) to
281 retrieve high-resolution, numerically continuous R_e and V_e . Comparisons with currently available
282 POLDER datasets indicate that the algorithm possesses improved capabilities in retrieving R_e .
283 Furthermore, the method can provide continuous values of V_e from 0.03 to 0.35, which are often
284 fixed or discrete in others^{28,29}. To ensure the accuracy of the retrieval results, eliminate the
285 influence of ice-/mixed-phase clouds, and facilitate subsequent data usage, Di Noia et al.³⁰
286 performed strict data screening and re-gridding on the retrieved data, resulting in a 1° × 1° dataset
287 containing only liquid cloud samples, referred to as L2-REGRID-REFF. The screening and
288 processing of data include:

- 289 1) The cloudbow scattering angle range observed by POLDER is between 135° and 165°;
- 290 2) The total cloud cover is greater than 0.95;
- 291 3) The cloud phase index is less than 50 (excluding ice clouds and mixed-phase clouds);
- 292 4) The cloud-top pressure is higher than 600 hPa (further excluding the influence of ice);
- 293 5) Data over the ocean is not affected by sun glint;
- 294 6) The data is from mid-to-low latitude regions with ample sampling points (60°S~60°N);
- 295 7) The data is re-gridded to the 1° × 1° grid with a daily (instantaneous) temporal resolution.

296 Due to the large volume of Level-1 data (several terabytes) and the high computational burden of
297 using the NNs algorithm, the L2-REGRID-REFF provided by Di Noia et al.³⁰ only includes results
298 from 2006. To ensure the subsequent analysis results have statistical significance, we further
299 excluded grid points with fewer than 10 valid samples throughout the year. Finally, we obtained
300 1,127,994 valid samples, of which 400,776 are land data and 727,218 are ocean data. This dataset
301 is referred to as POLDER-NNs and has been used in this study.

302 Cloud types in the POLDER-NNs dataset were classified based on the International Satellite Cloud
303 Climatology Project (ISCCP) cloud classification scheme⁵⁷. The results show that stratocumulus,
304 altostratus, cumulus, altocumulus, nimbostratus, and stratus account for 51.2%, 22.2%, 15.8%,
305 5.7%, 2.8%, and 2.4% of the samples, respectively, as illustrated in Supplementary Fig. 3. Notably,
306 stratocumulus clouds, despite their partly cumulus-like appearance, are typically categorized as
307 stratiform clouds due to their broad horizontal extent and limited vertical development⁵⁸. In
308 addition, due to the strict cloud cover criterion (cloud cover > 0.95 within the 5 km × 6 km grid),
309 the cumuliform clouds included here are limited to those with relatively large horizontal scales,
310 while small, isolated cumulus clouds (e.g., significantly smaller than 5 km × 6 km) are excluded.

311 In summary, the results in this study are primarily applicable to liquid-phase stratiform clouds
 312 (stratocumulus, altostratus, nimbostratus, and stratus, collectively accounting for over 78% of the
 313 samples). While some large-scale cumulus clouds are included in the dataset, the applicability of
 314 our findings to typical cumulus clouds remains uncertain and warrants further investigation.
 315 Additionally, this study specifically focuses on the impact of the dispersion effect on ACI. Since
 316 cumulus generally play a less dominant role in ACI due to their short lifetimes, small spatial
 317 coverage, and weak coupling with large-scale radiative processes⁵⁰, our focus on liquid-phase
 318 stratiform clouds aligns well with the primary goals of current ACI research.

319 **β and LN derived from POLDER retrievals**

320 In GCMs, R_e is generally parameterized through a PSD parameter β that relates R_e to the volume-
 321 mean radius (R_v)^{59,60}:

$$322 \quad R_e = \beta R_v = \beta \left(\frac{3LWC}{4\pi\rho_w N_d} \right)^{1/3}, \quad (4)$$

323 where LWC is the liquid water content (in kg m^{-3}), $\rho_w = 1000 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ is the water density, and
 324 N_d is the number concentration of cloud droplets that are assumed spherical. β can be well
 325 estimated by the relative dispersion (ε , defined as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean
 326 radius) by assuming a gamma distribution of the cloud PSD⁶⁰:

$$327 \quad \beta = \frac{(1+2\varepsilon^2)^{2/3}}{(1+\varepsilon^2)^{1/3}}, \quad (5)$$

$$328 \quad \varepsilon = \frac{\sigma}{R_m}, \quad (6)$$

329 where σ is the standard deviation, and R_m is the mean radius. However, both σ and R_m cannot be
 330 obtained through prognosis in GCMs. In order to calculate β in global models, different
 331 parameterizations were proposed.

332 In the early 21st century, parameterizations of the cloud PSD only considered the relationship
 333 between ε or β and N_d ^{9,17,20}. Later parameterizations gradually recognized the importance of
 334 LWC and began linking β with LWC/N_d (the liquid water mass per cloud droplet, hereafter LN),
 335 expressing their relationship in power-law form^{19,26}, as shown in equation (1). Additionally, two-
 336 moment cloud microphysics schemes in GCMs can prognosticate LWC and N_d directly⁶¹, making
 337 this form convenient for use in models.

338 According to the retrieval algorithm of POLDER, the PSD of liquid clouds (ϕ) is characterized by
 339 a gamma distribution^{52,62}:

$$340 \quad \phi(r) = Cr_c^{(1-3V_e)/V_e} e^{(-r_c/(R_e V_e))}, \quad (7)$$

341 where C is the intercept parameter, and r_c is the cloud droplet radius. Correspondingly, σ and R_m
 342 can be expressed in terms of R_e and V_e ⁶²:

$$343 \quad \sigma_P = \sqrt{(1-2V_e)V_e}R_e, \quad (8)$$

$$344 \quad R_{mP} = (1-2V_e)R_e. \quad (9)$$

345 where the subscript P indicates calculation using POLDER data.

346 Furthermore, ε and β can be derived from POLDER retrievals as

347
$$\varepsilon_P = \frac{\sigma_P}{R_{mP}} = \sqrt{\frac{V_e}{1-2V_e}}, \quad (10)$$

348
$$\beta_P = \frac{(1+2\varepsilon_P^2)^{2/3}}{(1+\varepsilon_P^2)^{1/3}} = [(1-V_e)(1-2V_e)]^{-1/3}. \quad (11)$$

349 It should be noted that the mode radius of the gamma function is $(1-3V_e)R_e$ ⁵², which means that
 350 the V_e should be less than 1/3 to ensure the existence of peaks in the gamma function (i.e., the
 351 mode radius is greater than 0). In the data provided by Di Noia et al.³⁰, the range of V_e is given as
 352 0.03 to 0.35. When conducting subsequent studies, the parts greater than 1/3 were excluded first.

353 According to equations (4) and (11), we can obtain cloud-top LN using R_e and V_e provided by
 354 POLDER (denoted as LN_P):

355
$$LN_P = \frac{4\pi\rho_w}{3} (1-V_e)(1-2V_e)R_e^3. \quad (12)$$

356 Exponentially fitting the β_P and LN_P yields parameter b (equation (1)), which can be used to
 357 quantitatively assess the global impact of DE on ACI, as described below.

358 **Impacts of DE on ACI**

359 The effective radiative forcing of aerosol-cloud interactions (ERF_{aci}) can be represented as the
 360 forcing sum of the Twomey effect (instantaneous effect) and the associated rapid adjustments^{3,16}:

361
$$ERF_{aci} = F_{Nd} + F_{LWP} + F_f, \quad (13)$$

362 where F_{Nd} , F_{LWP} , and F_f are the radiative forcing of the Twomey effect, and the radiative
 363 adjustments of LWP , and f , respectively.

364 Considering the dependence of cloud albedo (α_c) on cloud optical depth (τ_c)⁶³ and the relationship
 365 between τ_c with LWP and N_d ³¹, there are relationships in adiabatic clouds^{3,64}:

366
$$\frac{d\ln\alpha_c}{d\ln\tau_c} = 1 - \alpha_c, \quad (14)$$

367
$$\tau_c = \frac{6}{5} \pi Q_{ext} B^{\frac{2}{3}} \beta^{-1} LWP^{\frac{5}{6}} N_d^{\frac{1}{3}}, \quad (15)$$

368 where $B = [(4/3)\pi\rho_w]^{-1}(2c_w)^{-1/4}$, c_w is the adiabatic liquid water lapse rate ($c_w = dLWC/dz$,
 369 z is the height above the cloud base) and is considered to be constant through the cloud⁶⁴, Q_{ext} is
 370 the Mie efficiency factor and is usually set to 2^{31,65}, β is often set as a constant in ERF_{aci}
 371 calculation^{3,16}, and N_d is assumed vertically uniform in adiabatic clouds. Thus, equation (15) can
 372 be rewritten as

373
$$\tau_c \propto LWP^{\frac{5}{6}} N_d^{\frac{1}{3}}. \quad (16)$$

374 Correspondingly, F_{Nd} and F_{LWP} can be represented as³

375
$$F_{Nd} = \frac{1}{3} \alpha_c (1 - \alpha_c) \cdot c_{Nd} \cdot \Delta \ln N_{d,ant}, \quad (17)$$

376
$$F_{LWP} = \frac{5}{6} \alpha_c (1 - \alpha_c) \cdot c_{LWP} \cdot \Delta \ln LWP_{ant}, \quad (18)$$

377 where $\Delta \ln N_{d,ant}$ and $\Delta \ln LWP_{ant}$ are the anthropogenic perturbation of N_d and LWP . And c_{Nd}
 378 and c_{LWP} are the effective cloud fractions for N_d and LWP , respectively. Its “effectiveness” stems

379 not solely from the partial coverage offered by liquid clouds but also from considering the spatial
 380 correlations among other pertinent factors in deriving F_{Nd} and F_{LWP} ³. It should be noted that F_{Nd}
 381 here only considers the impact of N_d changes on R_e and consequently α_c , without accounting for
 382 β . Therefore, it can be regarded as part of the Twomey effect (referred to as the number effect).

383 In adiabatic liquid clouds, the vertical profile of LWC is termed the adiabatic condensation profile
 384 with a constant c_w :

$$385 \quad LWC(z) = \int_0^z c_w dz = c_w z, \quad (19)$$

386 and for LWP :

$$387 \quad LWP = \int_0^H c_w z dz = \frac{1}{2} c_w H^2, \quad (20)$$

388 where H is the cloud depth and c_w is approximately $2 \text{ mg m}^{-3} \text{ m}^{-1}$. Considering that satellite
 389 observations mainly capture information at the cloud top, here we relate equation (16) to the cloud-
 390 top LWC and N_d , denoted as LWC_{top} and $N_{d,top}$, respectively. Since N_d remains constant in the
 391 adiabatic cloud, $N_{d,top}$ equals N_d . Utilizing equation (19), we can derive LWC_{top} as:

$$392 \quad LWC_{top} = c_w H. \quad (21)$$

393 Combining equations (20) and (21), we obtain:

$$394 \quad LWP = \frac{LWC_{top}^2}{2c_w}. \quad (22)$$

395 Substituting equation (22) and $N_{d,top}$ into equation (16), we get:

$$396 \quad \tau_c \propto LWC_{top}^{\frac{5}{3}} N_{d,top}^{\frac{1}{3}}, \quad (23)$$

397 Although equation (23) incorporates β in the definition of τ_c (equation (15)), β is treated as a
 398 fixed parameter during practical implementation. As a result, variations in β cannot be accounted
 399 for when evaluating τ_c under anthropogenic aerosol perturbations (equation (16)), thereby
 400 neglecting the influence of the dispersion effect in the estimation of ERF_{aci} (equations (17, 18)).
 401 When the dispersion effect is considered (i.e., when β is treated as a variable rather than a constant),
 402 τ_c can be represented as⁶⁴:

$$403 \quad \tau_c \propto \beta^{-1} LWP^{\frac{5}{6}} N_d^{\frac{1}{3}}. \quad (24)$$

404 Given $\beta = a(LWC_{top}/N_{d,top})^b$ (equation (1)), and utilizing equation (23), we now can rewrite τ_c
 405 in terms of LWC_{top} , $N_{d,top}$, and the b parameter as

$$406 \quad \tau_c \propto LWC_{top}^{\frac{5}{3}-b} N_{d,top}^{\frac{1}{3}+b}. \quad (25)$$

407 Correspondingly, F_{Nd} and F_{LWP} , when considering the dispersion effect (i.e., F_{Nd}^{disp} and F_{LWP}^{disp}),
 408 can be written as

$$409 \quad F_{Nd}^{disp} = \left(\frac{1}{3} + b\right) \cdot \alpha_c (1 - \alpha_c) \cdot c_{Nd} \cdot \Delta \ln N_{d,ant} = F_{Nd} + 3bF_{Nd}, \quad (26)$$

$$410 \quad F_{LWP}^{disp} = \left(\frac{5}{6} - \frac{b}{2}\right) \cdot \alpha_c (1 - \alpha_c) \cdot c_{LWP} \cdot \Delta \ln LWP_{ant} = F_{LWP} - \frac{3}{5} b F_{LWP}, \quad (27)$$

411 where $3bF_{Nd}$ and $-3/5 \cdot bF_{LWP}$ represent the radiative forcing caused by the instantaneous DE
 412 (F_{DE_Nd}) and the adjusted DE (F_{DE_LWP}). Accordingly, the total radiative forcing caused by the
 413 dispersion effect (F_{DE}) can be expressed as:

$$414 \quad F_{DE} = F_{DE_Nd} + F_{DE_LWP} = 3bF_{Nd} - \frac{3}{5}bF_{LWP}. \quad (28)$$

415 To quantify the impact of the dispersion effect on ACI, we define the Dispersion Offset (DO):

$$416 \quad DO_{Nd} = -\frac{F_{DE_Nd}}{F_{Nd}} \cdot 100 \% = -3b \cdot 100 \%, \quad (29)$$

$$417 \quad DO_{LWP} = -\frac{F_{DE_LWP}}{F_{LWP}} \cdot 100 \% = \frac{3}{5}b \cdot 100 \%, \quad (30)$$

418 where DO_{Nd} and DO_{LWP} indicate the impact of DE on the number effect (i.e., the impact of
 419 instantaneous DE) and LWP adjustment effect (the impact of adjusted DE), respectively. Positive
 420 values indicate offsetting, while negative values indicate enhancement. The parameter b can be
 421 obtained by fitting the β_p and LN_p from POLDER-NNs, as described in equations (11) and (12).

422 **Explanation of the spatial distributions of β_p and LN_p**

423 In the main text, we pointed out that β_p and LN_p exhibit distinct land-ocean distribution
 424 characteristics. Here, we further discuss these characteristics.

425 The values of β_p over land are generally higher than those over ocean, reflecting the broadening
 426 effect of aerosols on the cloud PSD, which is consistent with previous analyses based on aircraft
 427 observations^{8,9}. However, even within the same oceanic or terrestrial region, β_p exhibits regional
 428 variations. For instance, over oceans, coastal areas, and regions affected by aerosols (such as the
 429 North Pacific) have higher β_p values compared to more open ocean areas (like the Southern
 430 Ocean). Similarly, over land, β_p also shows regional differences. For example, β_p values are
 431 higher in East Asia and India compared to the relatively cleaner Europe. Notably, β_p is higher over
 432 India than over the more polluted regions of China, which we think could be related to the abundant
 433 moisture conditions in India, though the specific mechanisms need further investigation. The LN_p ,
 434 which physically represents the amount of water vapor each cloud droplet can obtain, also shows
 435 land-ocean distribution characteristics. As shown in Fig. 1d, LN_p values are generally lower over
 436 land compared to ocean, which is associated with relatively less moisture and higher aerosol
 437 concentrations over land.

438 **Explanation of the spatial distribution of parameter b**

439 The distribution of parameter b varies significantly across different grid points (standard deviation
 440 of 0.015, with 0.013 in the dotted areas), exhibiting distinct spatial distribution characteristics.
 441 Overall, regions with $|b|$ are primarily located in areas heavily influenced by anthropogenic
 442 aerosols, such as ocean regions near continental coastlines, the northern Indian Ocean, the North
 443 Atlantic, the North Pacific, and low-latitude regions of the South Pacific, as well as land areas
 444 including East Asia, South Asia, the Indian subcontinent, central Africa, and southern North
 445 America. This indicates that the cloud PSD in these regions is more sensitive to changes in aerosols.

446 To explain the spatial distribution of parameter b , we plotted the relative changes in LN_p and the
 447 corresponding β_p (denoted as $\Delta \ln(LN_p)$ and $\Delta \ln(\beta_p)$, respectively) as shown in Supplementary
 448 Fig. 2a, b. The $\Delta \ln(LN_p)$ represents the difference between the mean $\ln(LN_p)$ of the highest 10%
 449 and the lowest 10% within a grid point, while $\Delta \ln(\beta_p)$ represents the corresponding difference in

450 $\ln(\beta_p)$. With a constant LWC , an increase in LN indicates a decrease in cloud droplet/aerosol
451 number concentration. Mathematically, using the principle of invariance of differential forms, we
452 have $d\ln(LN_p) = d(LN_p)/LN_p$, meaning $\Delta\ln(LN_p)$ represents the relative change in average
453 cloud droplet water content due to a decrease in aerosols. Similarly, $\Delta\ln(\beta_p)$ indicates the relative
454 change in cloud PSD due to a decrease in aerosols.

455 By slightly transforming the power-law relationship between β and LN (equation (1)), we get $b =$
456 $d\ln(LN)/d\ln(\beta)$. We attempt to approximate b using $\Delta\ln(LN_p)/\Delta\ln(\beta_p)$ (Supplementary Fig.
457 2c), thereby explaining the spatial variation of parameter b through the spatial distributions of
458 $\Delta\ln(LN_p)$ and $\Delta\ln(\beta_p)$. Comparing Supplementary Fig. 2c and Fig. 1e, the ratio of $\Delta\ln(LN_p)$ and
459 $\Delta\ln(\beta_p)$ shows a similar global mean and spatial distribution to the parameter b , indicating that
460 our analytical method is reasonable.

461 In general, the variation of $\Delta\ln(LN_p)$ exhibits a clear land-ocean distribution pattern. Compared to
462 land regions, oceanic regions have generally lower values with less pronounced regional
463 distribution features (Supplementary Fig. 2a). However, the variation of $\Delta\ln(\beta_p)$ in oceanic
464 regions shows distinct regional distribution characteristics, with larger absolute values mainly
465 occurring in the northern Indian Ocean, the North Atlantic, the North Pacific, and low-latitude
466 regions of the South Pacific, ultimately leading to larger absolute values of b in these areas. This
467 indicates that the spatial distribution of the fitting parameter b in ocean regions is primarily
468 determined by the relative variation of β_p , while the relative variation of LN_p across different
469 regions is not significant.

470 In contrast to oceanic regions, the spatial distribution of the fitting parameter b in land areas is
471 determined by the relative changes in both β_p and LN_p . For instance, in the Indian subcontinent, a
472 relatively small relative change in LN_p (Supplementary Fig. 2a) leads to a larger relative change
473 in β_p (Supplementary Fig. 2b), resulting in a more negative b in this region. In Europe, although
474 the relative change in LN_p is similar to that in the Indian subcontinent, the relative change in β_p is
475 relatively weaker, leading to a smaller absolute value of the parameter b . Similar results are
476 observed in other land areas. Overall, in land regions, the fitting parameter b is determined by the
477 combined relative changes in β_p and LN_p .

478 It is important to note that due to the limited variables provided by the POLDER-NNs dataset, our
479 analysis remains relatively coarse, and further analysis of the physical mechanisms is necessary in
480 the future.

481 **Factors influencing the $\beta - LN$ relationship over land and ocean**

482 In this study, we consider LN to be the dominant factor influencing β , and their relationship can
483 be represented by a power-law relationship. However, when LN is either small or large, the
484 relationship between β and LN appears to deviate from this power-law fitted using the pre-binned
485 method, particularly over land (Fig. 2e). In other words, when LN reaches extreme values, β may
486 be significantly affected by other factors. We speculate that this is related to the following three
487 factors:

488 1) Bias of the retrieval algorithm: Compared to the ocean, the retrieval uncertainty, especially for
489 large cloud droplets over land is greater³⁰. Further analysis suggested that this may be linked to
490 the influence of aerosols above clouds in these regions on the POLDER-NNs method³⁰. This effect

491 may cause β over land to become insensitive to LN when greater than 5 ng (Fig. 2e), thereby
492 reducing the fitted correlation coefficient.

493 2) Condensation (evaporation) occurring simultaneously with new activation (deactivation) for
494 small droplets: Lu et al.³² and Zhang et al.³³ demonstrated through in-situ observations and
495 numerical simulations that ε , which is proportional to β , shows a positive correlation with LN for
496 small cloud droplets. This may deviate the $\beta - LN$ relationship away from a negative correlation.
497 Compared to oceanic clouds, cloud droplets over land tend to be smaller overall, which may
498 contribute to the different fitting performance in land and ocean.

499 3) Collision-coalescence process for large droplets: When LN is large enough, the collection
500 process (precipitation initiation) may occur⁶⁶, thereby disrupting the original characteristics of β .
501 Considering that the retrieval of large cloud droplets over land is inherently less accurate, this
502 effect may be further exacerbated.

503 The above hypotheses regarding the land–ocean differences require further in-depth investigation
504 for validation.

505 **Process of uncertainty quantification**

506 The first source of uncertainty (Src1) arises from the inherent uncertainty in the POLDER-NNs
507 method. The POLDER-NNs dataset employed in this study is generated via a neural network
508 algorithm. Discrepancies between this dataset and the exact solution derived from the radiative
509 transfer model introduce uncertainty in the retrievals of R_e and V_e . Based on Table 3 from Di Noia
510 et al.³⁰, Src1 is found to cause a bias (*Bias*) and root mean square error (*RMSE*) in R_e/V_e of 0.08/
511 0.01 and 0.92/0.03, respectively, as shown in Supplementary Table 1. Based on this, we introduce
512 a bias-corrected random Gaussian noise for each R_e/V_e value in POLDER-NNs, denoted as
513 $N(-Bias, RMSE)$, where N represents a normal distribution with a mean of $-Bias$ and a standard
514 deviation of $RMSE^{1/2}$. Using the corrected values, we calculate β and LN , then fit the data to
515 obtain the parameter b and its corresponding standard error (*SE*) while accounting for the impact
516 of Src1. To ensure the robustness of the results and avoid potential biases from a single random
517 sampling, we repeat this process 10,000 times (Fig. 3a). The final estimates of b and *SE*,
518 considering Src1, are obtained by averaging all sampled results and are denoted as $b_{s1,d}$ and
519 $SE_{s1,d}$, where $s1$ refers to Src1 and d indicates the use of the direct fitting method (Supplementary
520 Table 1).

521 The second source of uncertainty (Src2) stems from the impact of cloud heterogeneity. The
522 POLDER-NNs data utilized in this study are characterized by a relatively coarse resolution, which
523 may introduce errors by assuming homogeneity within the retrieval area (~6 km resolution).
524 Therefore, it is essential to account for the effects of cloud heterogeneity on the retrievals of R_e
525 and V_e . Shang et al.³⁷ evaluated this impact by modeling a cloud field comprising several equal-
526 area subregions with constant cloud optical thickness but varying R_e and V_e values. Based on the
527 differences between the actual and retrieved R_e/V_e (as shown in Table 2 in Shang et al.³⁷), Src2 is
528 found to cause the *Bias* and *RMSE* in R_e/V_e of -0.71/0.02 and 0.88/0.04, respectively
529 (Supplementary Table 1). Following the uncertainty quantification framework from Src1, the
530 uncertainty in b caused by Src2 is then determined, and the $b_{s2,d}$ and $SE_{s2,d}$ are provided, as
531 shown in Supplementary Table 1.

532 The third source of uncertainty (Src3) arises from the use of the POLDER retrieval method,
533 wavelength selection, and grid-scale processing. The POLDER-NNs data are derived by applying
534 machine learning to the multi-angle, multi-wavelength polarimetric measurements with a grid
535 scale of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$. Shang et al.²⁹ introduced an enhanced primary cloudbow retrieval (PCR) algorithm
536 to estimate R_e and V_e from POLDER, creating a global retrieval dataset for four months (February,
537 May, August, and November 2008) (denoted as POLDER-PCR). Unlike POLDER-NNs,
538 POLDER-PCR employs traditional retrieval methods, clearly differentiating between various
539 retrieval wavelengths (670/865 nm), with a grid resolution of $0.7^\circ \times 0.7^\circ$. Data from POLDER-
540 PCR for low- and mid-latitude regions ($60^\circ\text{S} \sim 60^\circ\text{N}$) were selected for fitting parameter b . Based
541 on the fitting outcomes across two wavelengths, the uncertainty in b due to Src3 is determined,
542 and the corresponding b and SE are provided (denoted as b_{s3_d} and SE_{s3_d}), as shown in
543 Supplementary Table 1. Although POLDER-NNs and POLDER-PCR utilize different
544 wavelengths and grid scale configurations, as well as distinct retrieval methodologies, the derived
545 b values are relatively consistent. Compared to POLDER-NNs, the b values obtained from
546 POLDER-PCR exhibit larger SE , likely due to the smaller sample size of the POLDER-PCR
547 dataset (68,555 valid samples) and discontinuous V_e values (intervals of 0.02). However, this
548 convergence in b values obtained from two independent retrievals provides a basis for evaluating
549 the potential influence of Src3.

550 The fourth source of uncertainty (Src4) arises from the fitting method used for parameter b . As
551 discussed before, commonly used fitting methods for large satellite datasets include direct and pre-
552 binned fittings, though which of the two is the superior method remains unclear. Therefore, both
553 fitting methods were employed to derive b and SE using Src1 ~ Src3, as shown in Supplementary
554 Table 1.

555 Finally, the overall impact of four sources on the estimation of b is quantified using a Monte Carlo
556 method, similar to that of Boucher and Haywood³⁸ and Bellouin et al.³. It is assumed that the b
557 values induced by different sources, as shown in Supplementary Table 1, follow a normal function
558 (i.e., $b \sim N(b_{S_F}, SE_{S_F}^2)$, where S represents different sources, and F indicates the fitting method).
559 A random sampling process is then performed 10 million times, and for each random result, the
560 mean value of b affected by different sources is calculated, resulting in a probability density
561 distribution of b . The mean is then computed as the best estimate of b (-0.024), and the 5 ~ 95%
562 confidence intervals are determined as the uncertainty range for b (-0.026 ~ -0.022), as shown in
563 Fig. 3b and Supplementary Table 1.

564 Similar uncertainty quantification has also been applied to clouds over ocean and land, with the
565 relevant parameters listed in Supplementary Table 2 and the probability density distributions
566 shown in Fig. 3b.

567 Causal mediation analysis

568 To examine the relationship between aerosols, LN , and β , as well as the mediating effect of LN
569 on the impact of aerosols on β , we use the POLDER Level 3 aerosol products, generated using
570 Generalized Retrieval of Atmosphere and Surface Properties "components" approach, gridded at
571 a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ resolution (POLDER-3/GRASP, version 1.1)⁴¹⁻⁴⁴. This product is officially
572 recommended for studies involving both the Ångström Exponent (AE) and Aerosol Optical Depth
573 (AOD) and demonstrates a high consistency with the Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) on a
574 global scale^{44,67}.

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743 **Author contributions**

744 H. W., Y. P., and J. Q. designed this study. H. W. performed analyses and prepared the manuscript.
 745 Y. P. and J. Q. led this work and revised the paper. A. D. N and H. S. provided the POLDER data
 746 and advised the use of the data. H. L., B. D., O. P. H., and Y. L. gave instructive suggestions to
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748 **Competing interests**

749 The authors declare no competing interests.

750 **Tables**

751 **Table 1 Comparisons of results from this study, aircraft observations, and general circulation models**
 752 **(GCMs).** b is the fitting parameter. DO_{Nd} and DO_{LWP} are the impacts of the dispersion effect on the
 753 number effect and the liquid water path adjustment effect, respectively. Values in parentheses represent the
 754 5 ~ 95% confidence interval. The b of Martins and Silva Dias²⁶ is derived from the relationship between
 755 relative dispersion and the liquid water content per cloud droplet. The result of Xie et al.²³ indicates the
 756 total impact of the dispersion effect on aerosol-cloud interactions.

Data Source		b	$DO_{Nd}(\%)$	$DO_{LWP}(\%)$
POLDER	Global	-0.024 (-0.026 ~ -0.022)	7.2 (6.6 ~ 7.8)	-1.44 (-1.56 ~ -1.32)
	Land	-0.025 (-0.028 ~ -0.022)	7.5 (6.6 ~ 8.4)	-1.50 (-1.68 ~ -1.32)
	Ocean	-0.029 (-0.031 ~ -0.026)	8.7 (7.8 ~ 9.3)	-1.74 (-1.86 ~ -1.56)
Aircraft	Liu et al. ¹⁹	-0.14	/	/
	Martins and Silva Dias ²⁶	0.072	/	/
	Liu and Daum ⁷	/	10 ~ 80	/
GCMs	Peng and Lohmann ⁹	/	33	/
	Rotstayn and Liu ¹⁷	/	12 ~ 35	/
	Xie et al. ²³	/		7 ~ 14
	Wang et al. ²²	/	-13 ~ 10	/

757

758 **Figure Legends**

759

760 **Fig. 1 Spatial distribution of annual mean values for variables related to satellite data (POLDER-**
 761 **NNs) used in this study.** The first row shows variables directly provided by the POLDER-NNs dataset,
 762 including (a) the effective radius (R_e) and (b) the effective variance (V_e). The second row shows variables
 763 calculated from R_e and V_e , including (c) the particle size distribution parameter (β_P) and (d) the liquid water
 764 content per cloud droplet (LN_P). The third row presents (e) the parameter b by fitting β_P and LN_P within
 765 each grid point ($1^\circ \times 1^\circ$). The fourth row indicates variables derived from the parameter b , including the
 766 impacts of the dispersion effect on (f) the number effect (DO_{Nd}) and (g) the liquid water path adjustment
 767 effect (DO_{LWP}), where the dotted areas indicate the fitting relationships are statistically significant with a
 768 95% confidence level. The global mean and standard deviation are shown in the title of each plot, with
 769 those for the dotted areas provided in parentheses.

770

771

772 **Fig. 2 Relationships between particle size distribution and liquid water content per droplet across**
 773 **regions.** The x-axis represents the particle size distribution parameter (β_p), while the y-axis represents the
 774 liquid water content per cloud droplet (LN_p). The first row shows scatter density plots, and the second row
 775 displays joint histograms, all plotted with logarithmic scales on both axes. Panels (a, d) correspond to the
 776 global region (60°S ~ 60°N), (b, e) to land, and (c, f) to ocean. The solid black lines represent the fitted
 777 curves, and the fitting equations along with statistical parameters are labeled in the top right corner, where
 778 y means β_p and x means LN_p . For the scatter density plots, the color represents the frequency of data points
 779 within each small interval. And x_{avg} and y_{avg} mean the averages of LN_p and β_p , respectively. For the
 780 joint histograms, the color represents the probability density within this range, wherein each column is
 781 normalized so that it sums to 1. The black dot represents the median of β_p with an equal number of samples.
 782 The shaded area is the 95% confidence interval (according to a Student's t -test) to represent the fitting
 783 uncertainty.

784

(a) Flowchart of uncertainty quantification

(b) Probability distribution function of b

785

786 **Fig. 3 A framework of uncertainty quantification.** (a) The flowchart of uncertainty quantification, where
 787 b_{s_F} and SE_{s_F} represent the fitting parameter b and its standard error (SE) considering different sources of
 788 uncertainty ($S = s1, s2, s3$, representing sources 1, 2 and 3) and using different fitting methods ($F = p, d$,
 789 representing pre-binned and direct fitting methods). $N(b_{s_F}, SE_{s_F}^2)$ represents a normal distribution with
 790 a mean of b_{s_F} and a standard deviation of $SE_{s_F}^2$. (b) The probability distribution functions of parameter b
 791 in ocean, land, and global scales, where the point and errorbar represent the best estimate (i.e., the mean
 792 value) and its 5 ~ 95% confidence interval.

793

794

795 **Fig. 4 Relationships between cloud parameters and aerosol, along with results of mediation analysis.**

796 Joint histograms for (a) the liquid water content per cloud droplet (LN_p) and (b) the particle size distribution
 797 parameter (β_p) versus the aerosol index (AI) over the global region ($60^\circ\text{S} \sim 60^\circ\text{N}$), with both axes on
 798 logarithmic scales. (c) The result of mediation analysis, where ACMI and ADI represent the average causal
 799 mediation impact and average direct impact, respectively. The impact size means the change in $\ln(\beta)$
 800 due to a one-unit increase in $\ln(AI)$. The bar represents the mean impact size, and the error bar indicates the
 801 95% confidence interval.
 802